

Cyber Ethics, Data Security against Cyber Attacks

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Abstract:

Hacking is the expertise in any field that can be used for both ethical and unethical purposes. Those who perform hacking are known as Hackers. Therefore, hackers are classified as per their working and as per their knowledge. The ethical hackers are also known as white hat hackers. Ethical hackers use their hacking techniques for providing security legally. Generally white hat hackers are legally authorized hackers that work for Government. This paper explores the cyber world and cyber-crimes and its components over the internet. The fast-growing internet technology has benefited the e-commerce, e-mail, online banking or system, advertising, vast stores of reference material etc. But there is also a dark side internet becomes a common and easy tool for the criminal activity using the weak link and vulnerability of internet, the objective of this study is to understand the several hacking activities that come under the cyber-crime.

Keywords: Ethical Hacking, Cyber Crimes, White Hat Hacking, Cyber Security.

Introduction:

The protection of information and infrastructure is that security in which the chance of successful yet undetected theft, modification and disturbance of information and services are kept to low durable.

Network Security:

Protecting a network and data, computer program, other computer system assets from unwanted intruders, and unauthorized user.

Hacking and challenges:

A hacker is an individual who uses his technical skills with the help of computer and network to process the task. Hacker is a person who uses his efforts to gain unauthorized access to systems and networks in order to commit cyber-crime. He may steal all the important information like all bank accounts, all personal

data and use it to exploit the victim and ask for ransom wares to give data back.

Types of hackers in the present world:

White Hat Hackers:

Hacking for finding out the loop holes in the security system. White hat hackers, sometimes referred to as ethical hackers, assist system owners in detecting and fixing security systems vulnerabilities. They are referred to as ethical hackers because they do not violate laws, even though they use many of the same tools used by Black Hat hackers.

Table.1. White Hat Hackers

White Hat Hackers		
Mission	Personality Trait	Purpose
To protect organization	Ethical	White Hat Hackers are hired to find security holes or vulnerabilities in existing cyber systems, so they can be patched and security test.

(ii) Black Hat Hackers:

Hacking for illegal or malicious purposes. Black Hat hackers, sometimes called crackers, are typically motivated by the personal gain they

receive from illegally breaching computer systems, though they might also be social mischief-makers that are in it for the thrill of the attack, for revenge or to seek notoriety.

Table.3. Black Hat Hackers

Black Hat Hackers		
Mission	Personality Trait	Purpose
To profit from data breaches	Malicious	Black Hat Hackers conduct unauthorized and illegal cyber-attacks for stealing personal or organization information or data to sell for profit or personal use.

- **Grey Hat Hackers:**

Hacking sometimes legally and sometimes not but has no malicious intentions . Grey Hats can have ideological motivations that translate to hacking attacks against an adversarial political position, a company policy that they do not agree with or even a nation-state. They are

often referred to as activists. Grey Hat hackers can be White Hats by day and work for organizations and system owners to detect flaws in systems and mitigate them, but they sometimes engage in ideological hacking activities to correct a perceived wrong .

Table.4. Gray Hat Hackers

Gray Hat Hackers		
Mission	Personality Trait	Purpose
To challenge themselves	Ambitious	Gray Hat Hackers search for and exploit security vulnerabilities without profit and without authorization.

Ethical hacking:

Ethical Hacking has been used for software and network security]. Ethical hacking is performed with the target's permission.

Such type of hacking is intended to discover vulnerabilities from various types of future malicious attacks for betterment of secured system. It is the part of security enhancement program that cover risks and allowing cyber

security improvement penetrations legally. Ethical hacking can also be used for testing the security by vendors. Ethical hacking is performed in a controlled environment by performing ethical attacks. This helps better to understand the working of malicious codes and their range of dangerous areas. Generally, the ethical hacking term is used for security professionals for using their skills for defensive purposes to identify future security attacks in the system with good intention.

The term 'hacker' originated at MIT in the 1960's to describe someone who had the ability to understand and manipulate technology. Although this is still true of hackers, their skills have evolved outside of just technical capabilities to include the ability to manipulate people. Additionally, hackers are now categorized into three distinct categories that identify their motives.

Process of ethical hacking:

The preplanning is arranged in various steps for performing ethical attack to the system security testing legally. All technical, management and strategic issues must be considered. Proper planning is very crucial for security testing from simple password security test to all high level network penetration tests. Back up of data and information should be kept before committing ethical hacking. So, a well defined scope involves the following information

1. Specific systems to be tested.
2. Risks that are involved.
3. A proper test schedule is prepared over time.
4. Use knowledge or experiences to explore security threats.

What Is Cyber ?

The term cyber and cyberspace are modernized due to spread of computer and internet connectivity. Anything related to the

internet also falls under the cyber category. Some popular words that use the cyber prefix include the following: Cyber-crime, Cyberspace, Cyber forensics, Cyber bully, Cyber buck, Cyber security and Cyber punk.

Cyber Attacks and Cyber Security:

Cyber-attacks cause unauthorized access or manipulation, destruction, interruption in software in terms of malware intentionally to cause loss through electronic information or other physical infrastructure. There is a way to protect from these attacks is social awareness about cyber-crimes. It can be described as a process of applying information security measures or techniques to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) of information. Hackers can compromise the confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) of information by using social engineering attacks to naïve users.

Trends Changing Cyber Security:

The various impact of cyber security attacks on the communication infrastructures:

Web servers:

Web applications are used to extract data or information by using malicious code on servers. Such cyber criminals distribute their malicious code via their compromised web servers. Now we have to focus on the protection of web servers and web applications because web server contains the valuable information and data.

We should also use the safe web browser for financial transactions.

Cloud computing and its services:

The world is slowly moving towards the cloud. This latest trend presents a big challenge for cyber security against cyber attacks, as traffic can go around traditional points of inspection. Additionally, as the number of applications

available in the cloud grows, policy controls for web applications and cloud services will also need to progress in order to prevent the loss of important information.

APT's and targeted attacks:

Mobile Networks:

Common Cyber Attack:

- Un-targeted Attacks
- In un-targeted attacks, attackers randomly target as many devices, services or users as possible. They do not care about who the victim is as there will be a number of machines
- or services with weakness. To do this security issue, they use techniques that take advantage of the openness of the Internet, which include:
- Phishing - sending emails to large numbers of people asking for sensitive information (such as bank details) or encouraging them to visit a fake website.
- Water holding - setting up a fake website or compromising a legitimate one in order to exploit visiting users.
- Ransomware - which could include disseminating disk encrypting extortion malware .
- Scanning - attacking wide swathes of the Internet at random
- Targeted Attacks

Conclusion:

Ethical hacking is not a criminal activity but malicious unethical hacking is a computer crime or cyber-crime. The main goal of ethical hacking is to provide data and information security from being stolen and fraudulent use by malicious attackers. The concept of security and trust is very changeable because cyber threats can attack from any level of your organization. The

cyber-crime is growing day to day in a new innovation of crimes made by a class of intellectual and experienced cyber criminals. The cyber-crime is a great danger to the human rights in the digital world. Now-a-days the number of new security attacks being designed to steal personal information is increasing with accelerating pace. The attackers are targeting personal information to make a profit out of their operation.

References:

1. J. Gaia and G. L. Sanders, "Psychological Profiling of Hacking Potential 1," vol. 3, pp. 2230–2239, 2020.
2. Cybersecurity for Dummies by Joseph.
3. Hacking: The Art of Exploitation (2nd Edition) by Jon Erickson: Covers technical exploitation and security.
4. P. K. Paul and S. Aithal, "Network security: threat and management,"
5. F. Kwadade-cudjoe, "Effect of Cyber Security on Networks Operations (A case study of Vodafone).